

THE PEDAGOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

ZOKHIDA SHARABIDINOVNA TURSINOVA

Doctoral student, national research institute for professional development and training of pedagogues named after A. Avloni, Tashkent

zokhida87@mail.ru

Abstract: This article covers the concept of pedagogical competence, the importance of improving pedagogical development for teachers in all levels in Uzbekistan. Another issue highlighted in the article is the development of professional qualities of a foreign language teacher and opportunities created to fulfill the process. The author provides the information on types of competences teachers need before and while teaching. An attempt is made to reveal the core meaning of the concept ‘professional competence/teacher’.

Key words: *pedagogical competence, school language teachers, foreign language, certification, continuing professional development.*

Introduction

One of the current issues in the system of education is to lead and motivate the school staff, especially English language teachers to develop their pedagogical, psychological, methodological and overall professional competences. What does the professional competence of a teacher include? Is it connected with possessing the higher education diploma and higher band language certificate or is it the ability to deal with anything in the classroom and have the better result? Various aspects of the problem of developing professional competence are reflected in numerous psychological and pedagogical studies. These works give a general description of professional competence and the role of independent cognitive activity (Shchukin A.N., Balykhina T.M., Mamontov A.S., Danilov M.A., L.V. Zharova, G.S. Zakirov, E. N. Kabanova-Meller, M. I. Makhmutov, P. I. Pidkasisty, N. A. Polovnikova and others). Professor, Doctor of Pedagogy, Professor of the All-Institute Department of Theory and History of Pedagogy, Institute of Pedagogy and Educational Psychology, Moscow City Pedagogical University G.M. Kozhaspirova reveals the core concept of the notion as “The teacher’s possession of the necessary knowledge, skills and the traits which

determine the formation of his/her pedagogical activity, communication and the personality of the teacher as the bearer of certain values, ideals and pedagogical consciousness”.

Main part

According to E.F.Zera, competence includes not only a specialist's knowledge and experience but also the capacity to implement the amassed knowledge and skills in the present and put them to use while carrying out their professional responsibilities. Depending on the circumstance, the readiness and capacity to apply this knowledge is crucial in this instance. According to N.V. Kuzmina, "competence" refers to a teacher's capacity to transform a field in which he specializes into a tool for forming a learner's personality while taking into account the constraints and guidelines imposed on the teaching and educational process by the demands of the pedagogical norm in which it is implemented. The different types of competence are distinguished by N.V. Kuzmina:

- specialized and professional competence (in the discipline being taught);
- methodological competence (in the ways in which students acquire knowledge, skills, and abilities);
- socio-psychological competence (in the processes of communication);
- differential psychological competence (in the motives, abilities, and orientation of students);
- auto-psychological competence or reflection of pedagogical activity (in the field of merits and demerits).

Antoeva Yu.V. provides the general description in her ‘Conditions for the development of professional qualities of a foreign language teacher’(2020), which is noted below.

Professional competence of a foreign language teacher is a system of linguistic, sociolinguistic, cultural, strategic and discursive knowledge, skills and abilities that allow communicants to interact effectively in specific socially determined communicative situations, as well as skills and the ability to apply existing knowledge in the field of pedagogy, psychology and methodology foreign language teaching.

The professional qualities of a foreign language teacher can be divided into three groups. The first one is the knowledge of the language being taught (practical and theoretical) and the culture of the people - the native speaker of this language. The second group is the methodological knowledge and skills of the teacher, the third - pedagogical.

What criteria exists to reveal the core meaning of a competent teacher? The quote from Margaret E. Sangster, “No one should teach who is not in love with teaching” can concisely depict the core teaching belief. Some people say that in order to be a worthy instructor, it needs several years of experience, acquired teaching skills and qualifications while others think that a strong willingness to teach students and affection towards his/her profession make the teachers unique and professional in their field of area.

So what does it mean to be a ‘proficient’ teacher? It is true that there are a number of opinions and views on this very subject. And I would like to share my thoughts. As educators, we need to remember the adage of teaching being both an ‘art and science’. The art should include the reflective components that occur from within — such as internal motivators for improvement and evaluation, as well as engaging in reflection with colleagues both inside and outside of the profession. Perhaps most importantly, self-care in the form of becoming more prepared, relaxed and open to constant change is an essential component to being successful in this profession. We must also remember the “science” component of teaching, which includes external evaluations on content delivery and markers for improvement (e.g. administrator evaluations, student evaluations, and other quantifiable measures).

Innovativeness is the next component of professional competence. One should be an innovative teacher as to dare to go off the track in order to be on the track. Innovativeness is introducing changes and new ideas, daring to be different and being unique, experimenting new things, being fresh always. Moreover, updating one’s teaching and language skills is vital as new methods and approaches of teaching occur in the process of language teaching. Including digital tools and online activities which are preferred by young learners can be handy not only in interacting students in the class but also in assessing their knowledge economizing paper and teacher’s time.

A teacher who promotes interaction in the English class does justice to their profession by empowering learners and helping them develop their communication skills. Generally, motivating students; create opportunities for them to interact with one another through communication through entertainment activities such as role-plays, group discussions, mock interviews, etc. Even shy students, who sometimes don’t feel on their own plate, are fond of such classes.

In order to be an ideal teacher one should have 'passion' for the people s/he teaches, and his/her profession -which also means dedication; long hours, studying, paying for further development-and this happens because teaching is not only a job for a living it is also living for the job.

Patience is described as the ability to accept trouble and other people's annoying behavior without complaining or becoming angry. Learners are different in personality, so having such trait as to be patient is the most important factor in our occupation. As to have 'sweet fruit', or 'a good melodic music' to my mind, we - teachers must have all the skills which were mentioned above to educate and bring up astute and well-mannered students.

Conclusion

In today's improving world, a teacher must continuously learn, participate in self-education, and self-actualize through pedagogical activity in order to be professionally competent. The teacher engages in an appropriation-bestowal interaction as part of the self-realization process. A self-fulfilling teacher not only contributes to society but also invests in the ideals of his students. A teacher in the educational system is a self-developing individual who enhances both his professional and personal attributes through ongoing self-improvement.

All in all, it can be seen that each ideas and opinions have a considerable impact on how to be a skilled instructor in which it cannot be separated from each other. To be more precise, both academic knowledge and passion for teaching make every educator to be the best in their subject area.

REFERENCES:

1. Antonova Yu. V., Conditions for the development of professional qualities of a foreign language teacher, Retrieved from: https://xn--j1ahfl.xn--plai/library/professionalnaya_kompetentciya_uchitelya_inostrannogo_132621.htm
2. Artemov V. A. Psikhologiya obucheniya inostrannomu yazyku. — M.: Pedagogika, 1989. — p. 103.
3. Bim I. L. Nekotorye aktualnye problemy covremennogo obucheniya inostrannym yazykam. — YaISh. 2001, No. 4. — p. 39.
4. Balykhina T.M. Formation of the professional competence of a philologist at the stage of education in the magistracy. - M., 2000. - S. 111-127.

5. Bekmurodov M., K. Kuronboyev, L. Tangriev. Towards rapid development and renewal based on the strategy of actions- Tashkent: Publishing house named after Gafur Gulam, 2017, - 92 p.

6. Ibragimova, Sh. X. Professional competence of the foreign language teachers / Sh. X. Ibrahimova. // *Molodoy uchenyy*. — 2018. — No. 22 (208). — S. 315-316. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/208/50390/>

7. Saodat, Saidakbarova. "The Study of Phraseology and Its Theoretical Features." *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics* 11 (2021): 97-101.

8. Kodzhaspirova, G.M. Pedagogical dictionary / G.M. Kodzhaspirova. — Academy: 2001. — 672 p.

9. Kuzmina, N.V. Professionalism of the personality of the teacher and the skill of industrial training. Kuzmina. — M.: High school. — 1990. — 198 p.

10. Markova, A.K. Psychological analysis of the teacher's professional competence. — 1990. — № 8.7

11. Saodat, Saidakbarova. "THE BENEFITS OF USING CRITICAL INCIDENTS IN TEACHING LANGUAGES." *Conference. PERSPECTIVES OF IMPLEMENTING INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES TEACHING*. Vol. 11. 2021.

12. Passov E.I. Communicative foreign language education: concepts of individuality development in the dialogue of cultures. Lipetsk, 2000.

13. Sharobidinovna, Z. T., & Kabilovna, N. O. Comparative analysis of Lingvocultural aspects of proverbs and sayings about Parents and problems of Lingvodidactics (based on materials of Uzbek and English languages). 5. Malkina, N. A. (1996). Methodology of using skazki and obuchenii doshkolnikov ustnoy rechi na angliskom zyzyke.

14. Sharabidinovna, Z. T., Kizi, J. D. I., Azizovna, D. G., & Ruzikulovna, J. Y. (2020). CRITICAL PERIOD HYPOTHESIS IN ACQUIRING THE SECOND LANGUAGE: THE CASE OF TWO UZBEK STUDENTS. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(7), 881-884.

15. Zokhida Sharobidinovna Tursinova O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA SIYOSIY EVFEMIZMLARNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI // *Scientific progress*. 2022. №2. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/o-zbek-va-ingliz-tillarida-siyosiy-evfemizmlarning-qiyosiy-tahlili> (дата обращения: 25.03.2023).

